

OPTIMUM METHODS OF CALCULATING THE COMPOSITION OF ASPHALT CONCRETE IN THE CONSTRUCTION OF HIGHWAYS IN THE HOT-DRY CLIMATE OF UZBEKISTAN

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ANNOTATION This article describes the unique methods of constructing road pavements from asphalt-concrete mixture in the hot-dry climate of Uzbekistan. Scientists of Jizzakh Polytechnic Institute have developed several methods for calculating the composition of asphalt concrete, and this article is one of them.

Key words: asphalt concrete, road bitumen, mineral powder, strength.

INTRODUCTION. Asphalt concrete is one of the construction materials with a complex structure. Its complexity is that its properties depend on various factors and have drastic changes as a result of the temperature of the weather. These properties of asphalt-concrete are different from other construction materials used in road construction. Asphalt concrete exhibits its flexible state in positive weather temperatures and the opposite in negative temperatures.

LITERARY ANALYSIS AND METHODOLOGY. In the process of testing the standard samples made of asphalt concrete mixtures in the accredited laboratory of "Construction Products Testing" at the Jizzakh Polytechnic Institute, it was shown that the compression resistance at 50⁰C temperature is 10-20 kgs/sm², and at 35⁰C temperature it is 180-320 kgs/sm², and its strength approaches cement concrete strength. The change in air temperature has a dramatic effect on the deformation properties of asphalt concrete and the performance of the road surface [1,2]. These situations cause several difficulties in studying and managing the properties of asphalt concrete.

By now, many questions related to the properties of asphalt concrete and its use are being solved. Also in some sources there is [V.F.Babkov "Reconstruction of highways" Moscow. Transport. 2018., Kh.M. Karakulov "Use of modern materials

in the construction of highways” Guide. Tashkent, pp. 45-105., Construction according to urban planning standards 01.01.01-213 “Highways” Tashkent-2021., L.B. Gezentsvey “Asphalt-Concrete Road” Moscow “Transport” 1976] opinions on this matter, and in other sources [Construction of urban planning standards 02.05.02-21 “Highways” Tashkent-2021., GOST 9128-2013 “Asphalt concrete mixtures for road, airfield and asphalt concrete” (MTNKS) Moscow., Vehicle design standards. The Republic of Uzbekistan. 1998., J.A.Qosimov et al. Development of methods for improving the lessons of information technology on the basis of graphic programs //AIP Conference Proceedings. – AIP Publishing, 2022. – T. 2432. – No. 1., Gapparov B.N. Talabalarni ixtiroga jalb etish //Science and Education. – 2023. – T. 4. – No. 1. – P. 712-720., B.N. Gapparov Electronic scientific and practical periodical publication “Economy and Society”. ISSN 2225-1545. Issue No. 2 (93)-1 (February, 2022). pp. 264-270.] there are other opinions on this matter. Many conducted experiments and tests play an important role in ensuring the high quality of asphalt concrete and long-term durability of its condition on road surfaces. Our main goal is to apply the results of numerous scientific experiments and test works in practice [3,4].

In the production of asphalt concrete, waste from pebbles, obtained by crushing natural stone materials, is used as fine-grained sand. In the process of calculating asphalt concrete composition in the accredited laboratory of "Construction Products Testing" at the Jizzakh Polytechnic Institute, it was possible to create ways to reduce the costs of road construction works by conducting experiments with extensive use of local materials [5].

However, it should be noted that mature specialists of our republic say [*GOST 16557-2005 “Mineral powder for asphalt concrete and organomineral mixtures” (MTNKS) Moscow., GOST 12801-98 “Materials based on organic binders for road and airfield construction” (MTNKS) Moscow, Gapparov B.N., Umrzokov Z.A. “Basalt is the basis of modern composite building materials.” Architectural and*

construction problems of the Samarkand State Architectural and Construction Institute named after Mirzo Ulugbek (scientific and technical journal) 2021, No. 3 (part 1). Page 99-102., Gapparov B.N., Umrzokov Z.A. "Composite materials of the Jizzakh region." First Published in India in April 2022 by Moncheri Romance. Page 45-50., Gapparov B.N., Mansurova A.Sh. "Jizzax viloyatida mavjud kompozit materiallari." Yangi o'zbekiston: ilm qaldirg'ochlari - 2022" I-Respublika ko'rik tanlovi hamda talabalarning ilmiy -amaliy konferensiyasi (2022 May 14). 134-135 betlar.] on this matter, and others [Babkov V.F. "Road conditions and traffic safety" Moscow. Transport. 1993., Karakulov Kh.M. "Methodology for designing the composition of asphalt concrete using local materials in the dry hot climate of Uzbekistan." Ukraine. Priyaslav-Khmelnitsky. XXVI-International Conference-2020, March 24-26. pp. 136-139.] interpret this differently [6,7].

The amount of inert materials for 1000 kg of hot asphalt concrete is calculated in accordance with the requirements specified in the regulatory document **GOST 12801-98 "Materials based on organic binders for road and airfield construction"**. Samples of **GOST 9128-2013 "Asphalt-concrete road, polymer-asphalt-concrete, airfield"** were prepared on the basis of cross-linking of binder (bitumen) with inert materials in the accredited laboratory "Testing of construction products" at Jizzakh Polytechnic Institute. Determination of physical and mechanical properties of the technical condition of "Polymer-asphalt-concrete mixtures" was carried out [8,9].

RESULTS. According to the results of the conducted scientific research, the role of mineral powder obtained from the crushing of natural rocks together with local inert materials is of particular importance, it is the formation of its structure, the viscosity of the binder (bitumen), large and small size in the preparation of asphalt concrete mixture. It is characterized by the properties of absorbing oil and paraffin additives contained in the binder (bitumen). Currently, natural mountain

materials such as shale, diabase, and carbonaceous limestone are used as mineral powder in asphalt concrete production plants in Jizzakh region [10,11,12].

Many years of experience in the construction of asphalt concrete pavements show that if the technological process of preparing a hot asphalt concrete mixture from moderately selected materials is carried out correctly, that is, if the production technology is implemented at the required level, it will be durable for a long time, regular traffic a flow-resistant coating is formed [13,14].

DISCUSSION. In the accredited laboratory "Construction Products Testing" at the Jizzakh Polytechnic Institute, asphalt concrete composition design is mainly carried out using the SoyuzdorNII method, taking into account the weather of our republic, by checking the granulometric aspects and all qualities of the materials used [15]. Samples are prepared from selected materials for testing in laboratory conditions and their following properties are checked:

1. Granular composition of fillers
2. Water absorption
3. Expansion
4. Endurance at 20⁰C
5. Endurance at 50⁰C

The design of the asphalt concrete composition is carried out based on the technical assignment, in which the type of asphalt concrete, the conditions of use and application, the characteristics of mineral powder and binders are studied, and according to the results obtained, the current **GOST 12801-98 "Materials based on organic binders for road and airfield construction"** mineral powder consumption will be developed according to the requirements of the regulatory document [16]. Samples are prepared for testing according to the developed content. Test results of prepared samples according to the requirements of the regulatory document **GOST 9128-2013 "Asphalt-concrete roads, polymer concrete, airfield and polymer**

asphalt-concrete mixtures", the composition for the preparation of 1000 kg of hot asphalt concrete mixture is designed for the asphalt concrete production plant.

In the accredited laboratory "Construction Products Testing" at the Jizzakh Polytechnic Institute, samples were prepared for testing the asphalt-concrete mixture in 3-4 different ways (with an interval of 0.5%) from the optimal density of the selected materials, the optimal amount of bitumen and the selected amount of mineral additives. It was found that when activated mineral powder is added to these mixtures, the amount of bitumen consumed in the mixture is reduced to 0.5-1.0% and its consistency is normal [17]. Experimental tests carried out in the laboratory were directly used in the asphalt concrete plant of YXPTF enterprise of Jizzakh district, asphalt concrete mixture was prepared and used on internal roads of Jizzakh city.

CONCLUSION. The obtained results showed that as a result of the correct selection of the asphalt concrete composition, the correct selection of filler materials and the correct implementation of the technological requirements in the laying of the pavement, the pavements on the inner roads of the city of Jizzakh are distinguished by their durability for a long time period.

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